

Searching for New Physics in the Neutrino Sky

Carlos Argüelles

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Why search for new physics with astrophysical neutrinos?

Highest energy neutrinos

Extremely long baselines

Come from uncharted territories

Landescape of new physics with astrophysical neutrinos

Today:

Flavor and oscillation searches

Ultra-high-energy puzzles

See talks by Jure Zupan & Filippo Sala for DM-nu

Standard expectation:
Power-law energy spectrum

Standard expectation:
Isotropy (for diffuse flux)

Standard expectation:
 ν and γ from transients arrive simultaneously

Standard expectation:
Equal number of ν_e, ν_μ, ν_τ

Note: Not an exhaustive list

More: 1907.08690
Argüelles, MB, Kheirandish, Palomares-Ruiz, Salvadó, Vincent

Plan for the rest of this talk

1. Short recap. on neutrino neutrino beam and detector(s)
2. Searching for new physics in ultra-long baselines
3. Exploring the ultra-high-energy regime
4. Future

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**Intensity of
Neutrino
Emission**

IceCube 170922

MAGIC
detects emission of
> 100 GeV gammas

Fermi
detects a flaring
blazar within 0.1°

Multimessenger observations of a flaring blazar coincident with high-energy neutrino IceCube-170922A

The IceCube Collaboration, *Fermi*-LAT, MAGIC, *AGILE*, ASAS-SN, HAWC, H.E.S.S., *INTEGRAL*, Kanata, Kiso, Kapteyn, Liverpool Telescope, Subaru, *Swift*/*NuSTAR*, VERITAS, and VLA/17B-403 teams*†

“Neutrino emission from the direction of the blazar **TXS 0506+056** prior to the IceCube-170922A alert,” IceCube Collaboration. *Science* 361, 147-151 (2018).

**Identified
Neutrino
Sources**

NGC 1068

TXS 0506+056

Astro. ν_μ

Astro. $\nu_e \nu_\tau$

**All-sky
neutrino
emission**

**Intensity of
Neutrino
Emission**

Neutrinos from Our Galaxy

IceCube Collaboration, Science, 2023

Identified Neutrino Sources

Galactic Neutrinos

NGC 1068

TXS 0506+056

Astro. ν_μ

Astro. $\nu_e \nu_\tau$

All-sky neutrino emission

Intensity of Neutrino Emission

Summary of neutrino beam

All-sky flux

Diffuse, “all Universe” emission.
All flavors observed.
Mostly unassociated.
 $L \sim 1 \text{ Gpc}$

Point source flux

(Handful of sources)
Only seen in muon neutrinos
 $L \sim \text{Mpc to Gpc.}$

Galactic flux

Extended emission.
Observed in cascade events
 ~ 700 neutrinos associated
 $L \sim \text{kpc}$

Main detectors used today

A cubic-kilometer of ice/water instrumented with photo sensors.
~1 Gigaton target mass for neutrinos to interact.

Event signatures

Charged-current ν_μ

Up-going track

Factor of ~ 2 energy resolution
 < 1 degree angular resolution

Neutral-current / ν_e

Isolated energy
 deposition (cascade)
 with no track

15% deposited energy resolution
 10 degree angular resolution
 (above 100 TeV)

Charged-current ν_τ

Double cascade

(resolvable above ~ 100 TeV
 deposited energy)

ice vs. water

Short scattering length, long absorption length

10 TeV in ice

Short absorption length, longer scattering length

10 TeV in water

Water detectors are expected to have better particle identification capability.

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One of the most important questions in physics

Can we observe low-energy signatures of quantum gravity?

Oscillation from astrophysical sources

NGC 1068 (~ 14 Mpc)

$$L_{osc}^{eff} \sim E/\delta m^2$$

Galactic sources ~ 10kpc

$$L_{osc}^{std} \approx 10^{11} \text{m} \left(\frac{E_\nu}{\text{PeV}} \right) \approx 10^{-12} \text{Mpc} \left(\frac{E_\nu}{\text{PeV}} \right)$$

Oscillations are very fast: we measure flavor averages at Earth

After Flavor Oscillations: Where Would different sources end up?

Measuring a flavor composition outside of these regions points to new physics!

CA, T. Katori, J. Salvado
(Phys. Rev. Lett. **115**, 161303)

See also Bustamante et al. PRL 115, 161302 (2015); Rasmussen et al. 1707.07684; Palomares-Ruiz 1411.2998; Palladino et al 1502.02923; Bustamante et al 1610.02096; Brdar et al. 1611.04598; Farzan & Palomares-Ruiz 1810.00892; CA et al. 1909.05341; Learned & Pakvasa hep-ph/9405296 ..

Tau neutrinos are dominantly produced through oscillations

Instrumented volume

Tau neutrino measurements important to test oscillation physics

Identification by observing displaced vertexes

$$L_\tau \approx 50\text{m} \left(\frac{E}{\text{PeV}} \right)$$

Key observation in IceCube: tau neutrinos

- Total deposited energy ~ 90 TeV.
- First “bang” in time (shower)
- Second “bang” in time (tau decay)

IceCube, Eur. Phys. J. C 82, 1031 (2022); see also IceCube Phys.Rev.Lett. 132 (2024) 15, 151001

High-energy IceCube flavor measurement

Flavor measurement in agreement with standard scenarios

Very large errors due to small statistics

IceCube, Eur. Phys. J. C 82, 1031 (2022); Phys. Rev. D 104, 022002 (2021); see also IceCube, arXiv:2507.07212.

Search Low-Energy Effects of Quantum Gravity via Flavor Morphing

As neutrinos travel from their far away source they can interact with fields in space.

Example: spontaneous Lorentz violation.

Effects expected at the Planck Scale.

Space-time effects

J. Ellis et al arXiv:1807.051550

K. Wang et al. arXiv:2009.05201

Zhang & Ma arXiv:1406.4568

Flavor triangle trajectories in the presence of new physics

Introduce effective operators with given flavor structure

$$H \supset \frac{E_\nu^d}{\Lambda^{d-1}} \mathcal{O}_{\alpha\beta}$$

- (1 : 2 : 0) pion
- (0 : 1 : 0) neutron
- (1 : 0 : 0) muon-damped

IceCube collaboration *Nature Physics* (2022) arXiv:2111.04654

Planck-scale sensitivity with astrophysical neutrino flavor

Dimension-six operator scale constraint beyond Planck scale for some operators.

Model	Limits
IceCube Lorentz violation limit	$\hat{a}_{\tau\tau}^{(3)} < 2 \times 10^{-26} \text{ GeV}$
Dark matter potential	$V_{\tau\tau} < 2 \times 10^{-26} \text{ GeV}$
Dark matter effective Fermi coupling	$G'_F < 10^{-13} \text{ GeV}^{-2} (m_\phi / 10^{-20} \text{ eV})$
Dark matter non-standard interaction	$\epsilon_{\tau\tau} < 8 \times 10^{-9} (m_\phi / 10^{-20} \text{ eV})$
Vector dark matter coupling	$g_{\tau\tau} < 3 \times 10^{-33} (m_\phi / 10^{-20} \text{ eV})$
Axion dark matter coupling	$g_{a\tau\tau} < 3 \times 10^{-13} \text{ eV}^{-1}$

CA, Farrag, Katori arXiv:2404.10926

Horizontal axis represents astrophysical uncertainty on the initial electron to muon ratio.

One example out of many things that can be probed

Rasmussen et al, *Phys.Rev.D* 96 (2017) 8, 083018

What is the origin of neutrino mass?

Majorana

Dirac-like

If exactly Dirac: combine measurements from Cosmology or direct neutrino mass measurements and neutrinoless double beta decay.

If Quasi-Dirac: ultra long-baseline neutrino oscillation measurements

Neutrino telescopes!

Arkani-Hamed et al, 2007
Ooguri & Vafa, 2017
Hamada & Shiu, 2017
Gonzalo, Ibañez, Valenzuela, 2021
Vafa, 2024

Theory of neutrino masses

Beacom et al, 2003 (arXiv:hep-ph/0307151)
 Shoemaker & Murase, 2015 (arXiv:1512.07228)
 Esmaili, 2012

$$2\mathcal{L}_{\text{mass}} = m_D \overline{N}_R \nu_L + m_D \overline{\nu}_L^C N_R^C + m_R \overline{N}_R^C N_R + \text{h.c.}$$

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} 0_3 & M_D \\ M_D & M_R \end{pmatrix}$$

Expected to be the dominant contribution if neutrinos are Dirac-like

Lepton-number breaking term.

Dirac neutrinos: $M_R = 0$

See-saw scenario: $M_R \gg M_D$

Quasi-Dirac scenario: $M_R \ll M_D$

J. W. Valle Phys.Rev.D 28 (1983) 540

Dirac See Saw Scenario: Z. K. Silagadze, *Phys. Atom. Nucl.* 60, 272 (1997); A. S. Joshipura, S. Mohanty, and S. Pakvasa *Phys. Rev. D* 89, 033003 (2014); P.-H. Gu and H.-J. He *JCAP* 12, 010; E. Ma and R. Srivastava *Phys. Lett. B* 741, 217 (2015); J. W. F. Valle and C. A. Vaquera-Araujo *Phys. Lett. B* 755, 363 (2016); S. Centelles Chuli' a, R. Srivastava, and J. W. F. Valle *Phys. Rev. D* 98, 035009 (2018); Z. G. Berezhiani and R. N. Mohapatra, *Phys. Rev. D* 52, 6607 (1995), ...

Neutrino hyper-fine mass structure

Hyperfine splitting:

$$\delta m_j^2 \sim 10^{-22} - 10^{-12} \text{eV}^2$$

Oscillations from active to sterile neutrinos

$$|\nu_j^\pm\rangle = \begin{array}{cc} \text{active} & \text{sterile} \\ \hline \text{dark purple bar} & \text{light purple bar} \end{array}$$

J. W. Valle Phys.Rev.D 28 (1983) 540

Dirac See Saw Scenario: Z. K. Silagadze, *Phys. Atom. Nucl.* 60, 272 (1997); A. S. Joshipura, S. Mohanty, and S. Pakvasa *Phys. Rev. D* 89, 033003 (2014); P.-H. Gu and H.-J. He *JCAP* 12, 010; E. Ma and R. Srivastava *Phys. Lett. B* 741, 217 (2015); J. W. F. Valle and C. A. Vaquera-Araujo *Phys. Lett. B* 755, 363 (2016); S. Centelles Chuli' a, R. Srivastava, and J. W. F. Valle *Phys. Rev. D* 98, 035009 (2018); Z. G. Berezhiani and R. N. Mohapatra, *Phys. Rev. D* 52, 6607 (1995), ...

Relevant Oscillation Scales

M. MacDonald, K. Carloni, CA, I. Martínez-Soler, R. Alves Batista (arXiv:2512.10744)

- Three **high-energy** astrophysical sources:
 - **Point sources**
 - **Galactic** **This talk**
 - **Diffuse**
- Cosmogenic (L. P. S. Leal, et al. arXiv:2504.10576)
- Three **low-energy** astrophysical sources:
 - Solar (de Gouvêa et.al. 0906.1611, Donini et.al. 1106.0064, Ansarifard & Farzan 2211.09105, ...)
 - DSNB (M. MacDonald et al, 2409.16367, ...)
 - SN1987A (I. Martinez-Soler et al., 2105.12736, ...)

Oscillation from astrophysical sources

NGC 1068 (~ 14 Mpc)

$$L_{osc}^{eff} \sim E/\delta m^2$$

Galactic sources ~ 10kpc

$$L_{osc}^{std} \approx 10^{11} \text{m} \left(\frac{E_\nu}{\text{PeV}} \right) \approx 10^{-12} \text{Mpc} \left(\frac{E_\nu}{\text{PeV}} \right)$$

Oscillations in the presence of hyper-fine splittings

NGC 1068 (~ 14 Mpc)

$$L_{\text{osc}}^{\text{eff}} \sim E / \delta m^2$$

Galactic sources ~ 10kpc

$$L_{\text{osc}}^{\text{new}} \simeq 10 \text{ Mpc} \left(\frac{10^{-17} \text{ eV}^2}{\delta m^2} \right) \left(\frac{E}{10 \text{ TeV}} \right)$$

Oscillations observable in spectra of sources

$$P_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^3 |U_{\beta j}|^2 |U_{\alpha j}|^2 \left[1 + \cos \left(\frac{\delta m_j^2 L_{\text{eff}}}{2E_\nu} \right) \right]$$

$L \sim 14 \text{ Mpc}$

$\delta m^2 \sim 10^{-18} \text{ eV}^2$

Carloni, Martínez-Soler, CA, Babu, Bhupal Dev arXiv:2212.00737

Spectral distortions on a single source

$$P_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^3 |U_{\beta k}^* U_{\alpha k}|^2 \left[1 + \cos \left(\frac{\delta m_k^2 L_{\text{eff}}}{2E} \right) \right]$$

Averaged-out oscillations

“Dip” region

No change in signal

- Individual source flux uncertainties are large
- Energy resolution for muons is poor resulting in diminished signatures.

Solid: SM, Shaded: QD prediction with nominal astro model, Purple: QD with tuned astro model.

Sensitivity to hyper-fine splittings

Galactic neutrinos

IceCube measurements are compatible with neutrinos produced in cosmic-ray collisions with gas.

M. MacDonald, K. Carloni, CA, I. Martínez-Soler, R. Alves Batista (arXiv:2512.10744)

Effects of oscillation in galactic neutrinos

M. MacDonald, K. Carloni, CA, I. Martínez-Soler, R. Alves Batista (arXiv:2512.10744)

Observable effects of galactic neutrino oscillations

Observable effects of galactic neutrino oscillations

Observable effects of galactic neutrino oscillations

Let's look at all-sky IceCube astrophysical measurements

The total astrophysical flux is much larger, thus smaller statistical uncertainties.

All sky-flux has been measured in multiple flavor combinations.

⁷
tracks = ν_μ dominated
cascades = all-flavor

re-plotted from:
1. IceCube Collaboration, 2001.09520
2. IceCube Collaboration, 2402.18026

Let's look at all-sky IceCube astrophysical measurements

re-plotted from:
 1. IceCube Collaboration, 2001.09520
 2. IceCube Collaboration, 2402.18026
 3. IceCube Collaboration, 2507.22234

The total astrophysical flux is much larger, thus smaller statistical uncertainties.

All sky-flux has been measured in multiple flavor combinations.

Most recent combination shows evidence for break in spectra.

Can we use IceCube's diffuse flux measurements to constrain QD parameter space?

=> How is the total source population distributed across the universe?

*CombinedFit is does not include ESTES.

All-sky neutrino oscillations

1. Gröth, Ahlers, 2503.07718
2. Elías-Chávez, Martínez, 2503.07718

$$\Phi_\beta(E) = \int dz \sum_\alpha P_{\alpha\beta}^{QD}(E, L_{\text{eff}}(z)) \times f_\alpha \times \phi_0(E(1+z)) \times \frac{\rho(z)}{H(z)}$$

$P_{\alpha\beta}^{QD}$ = oscillation probability

f_α = initial flavor fraction

ϕ_0 = emission spectrum

$\rho(z)$ = redshift evolution of source population

New Constraints on hyper-fine splittings

Results (1): Assuming equal squared-mass differences, $\delta m_k^2 = \delta m^2$

Assuming source evolution following the SFRD and emission given by a broken power law.

No preference for a QD hypothesis.

Constrain $\delta m^2 \in [5 - 7.5] \times 10^{-18} eV^2$ at 3σ , driven by incompatibility at the break around 30TeV:

New Constraints on hyper-fine splittings

Results (2): Assuming two distinct squared-mass differences => flavor-dependent effects

QD oscillations caused by δm_1^2 disproportionately affect cascades, while those caused by δm_3^2 disproportionately affect tracks.

However, we find this additional flexibility does not significantly improve the joint fit (1.4σ)

Maybe neutrino decay?

Denton & Tamborra *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 121, 121802 (2018)

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Observation of KM3-230213A

Nature Volume 638 Issue 8050

$$E_{\mu} = 120^{+110}_{-60} \text{ PeV} \implies E_{\nu} \gtrsim 100 \text{ PeV!}$$

Neutrino or not?

- $\theta_{\text{zenith}} = 0.6^\circ \pm 1.5^\circ$, where the angular uncertainty is dominated by uncertainties in the absolute position of DUs
- Considering the natural overburden, an upper limit on the atmospheric muon background at 100 PeV:
 - $\ll 10^{-10}$ events per year within 2σ of the reconstructed direction
 - $\ll 10^{-4}$ events per year within 5σ of the reconstructed direction
- Atmospheric neutrino background above 100 PeV is approximately $(1 - 5) \times 10^{-5}$ events per year, dominated by the prompt component

KM3-230213A Within the Global Landscape

KM3NeT, *Phys. Rev. X* 15, 031016

Alex Wen

Nick Kamp

Is there tension between KM3-230213A and null observations from IceCube and Auger?

We consider a generic single-power-law flux model in the UHE region

Frequentist test

Parameter goodness of fit [1]

$$z_{\text{PG}} = 2.5\sigma$$

Bayesian test

Posterior predictive check [2]

$$z_{\text{PPC}} = 2.5\sigma$$

Is this the first time we are in this situation?

No!

Not our first ultra-high-energy anomalous event

ANITA-IV saw FOUR multi-EeV events

Event	$E_{\nu,\gamma=-1}$ (EeV)	$E_{\nu,\gamma=-2}$ (EeV)	$E_{\nu,\gamma=-3}$ (EeV)
4098827	$49.8^{+80.3}_{-37.7}$	$12.5^{+29.9}_{-7.4}$	$5.2^{+6.0}_{-2.5}$
19848917	$31.9^{+76.0}_{-24.5}$	$5.2^{+11.0}_{-2.9}$	$2.6^{+3.1}_{-1.1}$
50549772	$45.4^{+83.4}_{-34.4}$	$8.8^{+19.5}_{-4.9}$	$4.3^{+4.8}_{-2.1}$
72164985	$60.3^{+88.9}_{-38.2}$	$15.1^{+27.3}_{-7.6}$	$8.9^{+10.5}_{-4.5}$

Are things consistent?

CA, Bertólez-Martínez, Burgos, Burns, Lopez-Pavon, and Salvado et al, arXiv:2510.21929

Big problem!

Uncomfortable, but we okish.

A “toy” scenario for ANITA+KM3NeT

CA, Bertólez-Martínez, Burgos, Burns, Lopez-Pavon, and Salvado et al, arXiv:2510.21929

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Specialized Neutrino Telescopes

*Energy ranges here are only approximate and meant for illustration, not to be taken at face value.

How do we detect high-energy tau neutrinos?

Instrumented volume

$$N_\tau \sim \sigma_{\nu p} \Phi_\nu L_{detector}$$

Identification by separating “bangs”

$$L_\tau \approx 50\text{m} \left(\frac{E}{\text{PeV}} \right)$$

Backgrounds: mis-reco, D-mesons.

How do we detect high-energy tau neutrinos?

Tau neutrino "double bangs" are increasingly rarer to contain.

Tau neutrino identification in volumetric detector becomes inefficient.

How do we detect **ultra** high-energy tau neutrinos?

$$N_{\tau} \sim \sigma_{\nu p} \Phi_{\nu} L_{\tau}^0 \cdot \frac{E}{m_{\tau}}$$

High tau purity
increasing “efficiency” with energy!

Many neutrino telescope proposals! Various underway

NOTE
 PROJECTS MARKED IN **BLUE** ARE COMPLETE OR UNDER CONSTRUCTION.
 PROJECTS MARKED IN **WHITE** ARE PROPOSED.

TAMBO: An ultra-high-energy neutrino telescope

Design goal: Aim to go as low as possible in energy: 1 PeV to 100 PeV range

With ~ 5000 modules we have comparable or greater effective areas for identified taus

TAMBO Collaboration, arXiv:2507.08070

Status of TAMBO

Today

TAMBO-4

Small test array
Electronics, detector
prototypes

2025-2028

TAMBO-100
(aka TAMBITO)

Pilot array
Deployment techniques,
background, and social science

Funded!

2028 - ...

TAMBO-5k

Array capable of detecting O(1)
neutrinos per year in the PeV to
100 PeV energy range

Flavor Complementarity

Alba Burgos, CA, W. Thompson, to appear

$E_\nu > 100 \text{ PeV}$

In-ice radio

Earth-skimming ν_τ

Combined

**In searching for new physics with
astrophysical neutrinos with live in
exciting times**

Thanks!

the David & Lucile Packard FOUNDATION

JOHN TEMPLETON FOUNDATION

Carlos A. Argüelles — 2026

The non-observation of point sources requires sources to be very dim and dense if you assume flat evolution
— see Capel et. al. (2017).

- f_α = pion decay
- ϕ_0 = BPL
- $\rho(z) \sim$ SFRD

Constraints based on the *CombinedFit* measurements are consistent with those using *Cascades* and *ESTES*.

The oscillation probability depends on $L_{\text{eff}}(z) = \int_0^z \frac{dz'}{H(z')(1+z')^2}$

Note:
 Capel, Mortlock, Finley (2022)
 found that IceCube's non-
 observation of point sources
 requires sources to be very
 dim and dense if you assume
 flat evolution.

Capel, Mortlock, Finley, 2005.02395

Scale as $(1+z)^m$ at small z , for $m = 0, 3, 5$

NGC 1068: The brightest Steady Neutrino Emittor In the Nothern Hemisphere

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RESEARCH ARTICLE | NEUTRINO ASTROPHYSICS

Evidence for neutrino emission from the nearby active galaxy NGC 1068

KM3NeT: Water Neutrino Telescope

31 3" photo-multiplier tubes per Digital Optical Module (DOM)

18 DOMs per Detection Unit (DU)

50 strings already deployed near Sicily!

Each DU is unraveled before reaching the sea floor

IceCube Gen-2

Phase 2: x8 the volume of present IceCube, plus additional detectors.

The IceCube Upgrade

Phase 1: 7 new, high-precision strings in the central, densely instrumented region. Funded, installation in 2025.

Improved light-collection for low-energy events

*DeepCore (shown on the left) is the current low-energy extension of IceCube

Improvements through Machine Learning

F. J. Yu, J. Lazar, and CA arXiv:2303.08812

M. Jin, Y. Hu, CA [2311.04983](#)

F. J. Yu, N. Kamp, CA arXiv:2408.08474

F. J. Yu, N. Kamp, CA arXiv:2410.13148

P. Rodriguez-Grasa, P. Zhelnin, et al arXiv:2506.16530

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TAPAY
Town

CABANAACONDE

Proposed
TAMBO
Location

τ

ν

τ

We went to Peru in 2023 and found a potential location for the experiment!

Status of TAMBO

Today

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Small test array
Electronics, detector
prototypes

2025-2028

TAMBO-100
(aka TAMBITO)

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TAMBO-5k

Array capable of detecting $O(1)$
neutrinos per year in the PeV to
100 PeV energy range

Expected reach of TAMBO

Flux of neutrinos scaled by energy

W. Thompson

P. Zhelnin

TAMBO Backgrounds

- Mountain acts as filter for muon backgrounds
- Neutrino purity tunable based on column depth requirement

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Search Low-Energy Effects of Quantum Gravity via Flavor Morphing

As neutrinos travel from their far away source they can interact with fields in space.

Example: spontaneous Lorentz violation.

Effects expected at the Planck Scale.

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J. Ellis et al arXiv:1807.051550

K. Wang et al. arXiv:2009.05201

Zhang & Ma arXiv:1406.4568

Effects of flavor transformations

$$H \sim \frac{m^2}{2E} + a^{(3)} - c_{\mu}^{(4)} p^{\mu} + a_{\mu\nu}^{(5)} p^{\mu} p^{\nu} - c_{\mu\nu\lambda}^{(6)} p^{\mu} p^{\nu} p^{\lambda} + \dots \longrightarrow P_{\alpha\beta} \sim \sin^2(L \cdot \rho_d \cdot E^{d-3})$$

increasing LV-parameter strength

Planck-scale constraints on Lorentz violating operators

Planck-scale sensitivity with astrophysical neutrino flavor

Detection of tau neutrino constraints all models that suppress tau appearance.

Constraints of neutrino flavor transition can be interpreted in various models

Model	Limits
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CA, Farrag, Katori arXiv:2404.10926

IceCube collaboration *Nature Physics* (2022) arXiv:2111.04654

Constraints on Lorentz Invariance Violation

Alex Wen

- Superluminal neutrinos lose energy via vacuum Cherenkov radiation ($\nu \rightarrow \nu e^+ e^-$)

- $\Gamma \propto E^5 \delta^3$, where $\delta \equiv c_\nu^2 - 1$
- Thus, a high energy neutrino can set a strong upper limit on δ

Method	Limit
IceCube atmospheric	6.2×10^{-11}
IceCube NGC 1068	1.5×10^{-15}
IceCube TXS 0506+056	2.4×10^{-18}
Stecker et al. (Ref. [20])	5.2×10^{-21}
KM3-230213A (conservative)	1.8×10^{-21}
KM3-230213A (likely)	4.2×10^{-22}

KM3NeT, *Nature Communications*, arXiv:2502.12070

Long-standing anomalies on “appearance” searches

LSND
(3.8 σ !)

These experiments observe ν_e appearance at $L/E \sim 1 \text{ km/GeV}$!

This points to $\Delta m^2 \sim 1 \text{ eV}^2$

MiniBooNE
(4.8 σ !)

Other interesting observations or lack of them

Several experimental searches at relevant energy to
baseline ratio

	$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e$	$\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu$	$\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e$
Neutrino	MiniBooNE (BNB) *	SciBooNE/MiniBooNE	KARMEN/LSND Cross Section
	MiniBooNE(NuMI) NOMAD	CCFR CDHS	Gallium * BEST *
	MicroBooNE (BNB) (*?)	MINOS IceCube	
Antineutrino	LSND *	SciBooNE/MiniBooNE	Bugey Daya Bay NEOS PROSPECT
	KARMEN	CCFR MINOS	DANSS STEREO
	MiniBooNE (BNB) *	IceCube (*?)	Neutrino-4 *

Lack of a consistent picture makes this situation confusing!
No consistent global solution exists.

* \Rightarrow $>2\sigma$ “signal”

An overconstrained problem: Appearance and disappearance signals related

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e \\
 \nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e \\
 \nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu
 \end{array}
 \quad \Rightarrow \quad
 \boxed{U_{e4}} \quad \boxed{U_{\mu4}} \quad \boxed{\Delta m^2}$$

$$P_{\nu_e \rightarrow \nu_e} = 1 - 4 \boxed{(1 - |U_{e4}|^2) |U_{e4}|^2} \sin^2(1.27 \boxed{\Delta m_{41}^2} L/E)$$

$$P_{\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_e} = 4 \boxed{|U_{e4}|^2} \boxed{|U_{\mu4}|^2} \sin^2(1.27 \boxed{\Delta m_{41}^2} L/E)$$

$$P_{\nu_\mu \rightarrow \nu_\mu} = 1 - 4 \boxed{(1 - |U_{\mu4}|^2) |U_{\mu4}|^2} \sin^2(1.27 \boxed{\Delta m_{41}^2} L/E)$$

$$\sin^2 2\theta_{ee} = 4(1 - \boxed{|U_{e4}|^2}) \boxed{|U_{e4}|^2}$$

$$\sin^2 2\theta_{\mu\mu} = 4(1 - \boxed{|U_{\mu4}|^2}) \boxed{|U_{\mu4}|^2}$$

$$\sin^2 2\theta_{\mu e} = 4 \boxed{|U_{\mu4}|^2} \boxed{|U_{e4}|^2}$$

Appearance and disappearance “preference regions” don’t overlap!

Results from the latest
Columbia-Harvard-MIT Global Fit
Hardin et al. arXiv:2211.02610.

Similar conclusions from
other groups see Gariazzo
et al. 1703.00860, and
Dentler et al JHEP 1808
(2018). See Diaz et al.
arXiv:1906.00045 for more
discussion.

Dark matter annihilation

IceCube Collaboration 2205.12950.
 See also CA, H. Dujmovic arXiv
 1907.11193, Dekker et al
 1910.12917; Chianese et al.
 1907.11222; Sui & Bhupal Dev
 1804.04919; Feldstein et al
 1303.7320; Murase et al 1503.04663,
 Murase & Beacom 1206.2595 ...

See talk by Fabrizio Vassallo

Dark matter annihilation to neutrino: a largely unexplored frontier

CA, A. Diaz, A. Kheirandish, A. Olivares-Del-Campo, I. Safa, A.C. Vincent
Rev. Mod. Phys. **93**, 35007 (2021);
 See also Beacom et al. *PRL* **99**: 231301, 2007.
 See also CA, D. Delgado, A. Friedlander, A. Kheirandish, I. Safa, A.C. Vincent, H. White
 (arXiv:2210.01303) for a recent review focused on dark matter decay

Dark matter scattering with neutrinos

See also talk by Bei Zhou

CA, A. Kheirandish & A. Vincent Phys. Rev. Lett. **119**, 201801

Dark matter scattering with neutrinos

$$E_\nu > 60 \text{ TeV}$$

Constraints comparable to cosmology

Dark matter scattering with neutrinos: new analysis!

Work by Diya Delgado

A. McMullen, A. Vincent, CA, A. Schneider arXiv:2107.11491

Larger sample sizes data sets yet to be used for these searches.
 Only IceCube's High-Energy Starting Events used so far.

Thinking about Earth-skimming neutrino detectors

The geometry here is key for the acceptance of neutrino detection

Thinking about Earth-skimming neutrino detectors

The geometry here is key for the acceptance of neutrino detection
This would be a more ideal scenario, but can't put mountain over detector

Pavel Zhelmin

William Thomson

Diya Delgado

Jeffrey Lazar

Ibrahim Safa

And many others ...

AIR SHOWER:

3 - 10 KM LENGTH
200 M DIAMETER

DECAY

RANGE:
50 M - 5 KM

ROCK

> 4 KM SHIELDING FROM
BACKGROUND MUONS

CHARGED-CURRENT
INTERACTION

~100 M
SEPARATION

WATER CHERENKOV
DETECTOR ARRAY

~M³ EACH

DEEP VALLEY

TAU AIR-SHOWER MOUNTAIN-BASED OBSERVATORY (TAMBO) • COLCA VALLEY, PERU

We went to Peru earlier last year and found a location for the experiment!
First prototype detectors now in Peru.

TAMBO Simulation

J. Lazar, P. Zhelnin, W. Thompson for the TAMBO Collaboration (2025, to arXiv)

TAMBO Simulation

J. Lazar, P. Zhelnin, W. Thompson for the TAMBO Collaboration (2025, to arXiv)

Design goal: Aim to go as low as possible in energy: 1 PeV to 100 PeV range

P. Zhelnin, W. Thompson for the TAMBO Collaboration (2025, to arXiv)

With ~ 5000 modules we have IceCube-EHE comparable or greater effective areas

Expected reach of TAMBO

Expected rates at TAMBO given unknown-origin IceCube flux

**Neutrino astronomy has started with first high-significance sources.
Exponentially growing field expected.**